

EVALUATING THE PERFORMANCE OF MICROBIAL ELECTROLYSIS CELLS WITH MODIFIED CARBON ELECTRODES IN REAL BILGE WATER TREATMENT AND METHANE PRODUCTION

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Abstract

A coupled microbial cell (MEC) – anaerobic granular sludge system was settled to investigate the ability of different carbon modified electrodes to enhance biodegradation of undiluted bilge water (BW) and increase methane generation. MEC is an emerging technology for converting organic matter into value-added products such as methane. According to the results, 3D graphene found to be the most promising among the three tested materials. CH₄ content reached 62% in just 10 days after feeding of the anaerobic granular sludge with 50% of real undiluted bilge water and application of 1V. Regarding chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal values as high as 63% were observed. Among different Volatile Fatty Acids (VFAs) normally detected during anaerobic treatment, acetic acid was the most abundant.

INTRODUCTION

BW is a combination of seawater and several types of wastes such as like fuels, detergents, solid particles, lubricating and hydraulic oils, and so on (Emadian et al., 2015; Vyrides et al., 2018). According to the literature high COD concentrations (2 g L⁻¹) and salinity values (25 and 35 g L⁻¹) inhibit severely its biological treatment. The aim of this study was to examine the efficiency of carbon modified electrodes on the biodegradation of undiluted real bilge water during batch experiments using anaerobic granular sludge as an inoculum. Three different materials were synthesised and examined including carbon foam, carbon cloth decorated with metallic nanoparticle and 3D graphene. Application of 1V of external potential was investigated as a strategy to increase both CH₄ generation and COD removal. For more than a month, biogas production and composition, soluble COD and VFAs concentration were monitored.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental protocols

AGS was collected from a full-scale upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) treating dairy wastewater at pH 7.0–7.5. Before its use as inoculum, AGS was washed, flashed with CO₂ and placed in 34°C for a week. Real BW was collected from Ecofuel Ltd (Zygi, Cyprus) which gathers and treats this type of wastewater. Batch lab-scale experiments were conducted in 1L reactors with a working volume of 0.7L. Each reactor was fed with 50 g of AGS and BW in different concentrations (Phase 1: 50%, Phase 2: 75%) for two consecutive batch cycles. The remained volume was filled with anaerobic medium (Angelidaki et al., 2009) and sealed. Anaerobic conditions were achieved by flushing CO₂ inside (5 min). The pH of the liquor was adjusted to 7.5. The reactors were placed at

34 °C for a period of more than a month. Four reactors were run simultaneously as follows: R0 (without electrodes inside) which was the control, R1 (contained carbon foam electrodes), R2 (contained carbon cloth decorated with metallic nanoparticles electrodes) and R3 (3D graphene electrodes). Carbon modified electrodes were synthesized in the Nano/Micro Mechanics of Materials Laboratory. All of them were prepared using T-CVD quartz tube under specific low-pressure conditions according to Constantinou et al. (2018) and were characterized using Scanning Electron Microscopy, Atomic Force Microscopy, X-ray Diffraction. Performance of the MECs was studied by applying a constant potential of 1.0V. Headspace and liquid samples were taken over time for gas composition determination, estimation of COD removal and Fatty Volatile Acids (VFAs) measurement. Throughout the experiments, the output voltage in reactors was also recorded every 5 minutes by a data acquisition system (Keithley 2700) connected to a computer.

Analytical techniques

Samples taken from MECs were filtered (0.22 µm) and COD was measured according APHA (2005). Biogas volumes were regularly measured using a 50 ml glass syringe while its composition (H₂, O₂, N₂, CH₄, and CO₂ concentrations) was determined by withdrawing 1 mL from the headspace and analyzing it in a Gas Chromatographer equipped with Thermal Conductivity Detector (GC-TCD) (Vyrides et al., 2018). VFAs (formic, acetic, propionic and butyric acid) were determined using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) at 210 nm (Vyrides and Stuckey, 2009). The current across the resistor (10 mΩ) in MECs were collected by an automatic data acquisition system (Keithley 2750, Tektronix, USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the results, higher methane production was observed in R3 reactor which run with 3D graphene electrodes inside followed by R2 and R1. During Phase 1 of the experiment (use of 50% BW) methane content in R3 was determined to be 24% in 24h and reached almost 62% in 10 days. After that period, it remained stable up to day 13 (end of Phase 1). On the contrary, in R1 and R2 reactors % CH₄ reached its maximum value during the first 3 days (R1: 27%, R2: 43%) and then began to reduce over time. The replacement part of liquor on day 13 with fresh BW (start of Phase 2 with 75% BW), resulted in the same patent in methane generation in the three reactors. Regarding COD removal, during Phase 1 values equal to 63%, 29% and 16% were observed in R3, R2 and R1, respectively. As for the Phase 2, similar trend was observed concerning COD. Chromatographic analysis of liquid samples for the existence of VFAs, confirmed the presence compounds such as acetic acid and valeric acid. The results demonstrated that among the three different electrodes examined in the present study, 3D graphene seems to be a promising material for the removal of organic load and for methane production during anaerobic digestion of refractory and complex substrates such as bilge water.

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